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Unlocking Efficiency: Assessing the Impact of PromptPay on Government Operations and Financial Transactions in Thailand

Asst. Prof. Dr. Marisa Laokulrach, International College,
National Institute of Development Administration of NIDA, Thailand

Assoc. Prof. Dr. Aweewan Pamyagometh, International College,
National Institute of Development Administration, Thailand

Prof. Dr. Anetta Čaplánová, University of Economics in Bratislava, Slovakia

Extended abstract

PromptPay is the national digital payment system developed by the government in Thailand in 2016. It was first launched in 2017 to promote cashless transactions and increase payment efficiency. The system was developed in collaboration with major commercial banks and financial institutions. It is a real-time electronic fund transfer system that allows users to transfer and receive money. People can register to the system using a mobile number or Thai national ID. Number and use it for money transactions to bypass traditional bank account numbers. Currently, there are about 51 million registrations with a recorded value of 75.9 million transactions per day, with an average value of 130 billion Thai Baht (THB) in 2023. Bank of Thailand (BOT) continues to develop the digital payment infrastructure to promote financial inclusion and economic growth. PromptPay has led to a decrease in cash withdrawals from 2019-2023. PromptPay often has lower transaction fees than traditional banking methods. Some transactions, tiny ones, are free of charge. PromptPay supports online transactions for the business sectors, making it easier for businesses to accept payments and for consumers to shop online. PromptPay encourages more people to engage in e-commerce, supporting the growth of Thailand's digital economy.

The PromptPay system is utilized for various services, including Thai QR payment, C2C transfer, e-Wallet, PromptPay for business, cross-bank bill payment, cross-border payment connectivity, tax reimbursement, E-donation, social welfare distribution, and other government subsidies.

This study explores how PromptPay services can enhance government efficiency, reduce corruption, and promote a cashless society in Thailand. Cost-benefit analysis (CBA) is a fundamental tool employed in various fields to evaluate the feasibility and desirability of projects, policies, and interventions. The costs and benefits associated with Promptpay have been gathered from various credible sources. The quantity of money circulation since the program is being practiced is analyzed to identify the promotion of a cashless society from the nation's broad use of PromptPay for government programs and financial transactions. The preliminary results of some services from PromptPay identify the efficient use of the system in order to reduce corruption, enhance government efficiency, and increase a cashless

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society. Tax reimbursement service via check is replaced by PromptPay transfers instead, starting in 2017 onwards, to prevent fraudulent processes. PromptPay is an alternative system designed to enhance convenience in making and receiving money transfers from government agencies. Additionally, it helps save operational costs by at least 40 Thai Baht per transaction, eliminating the need for issuing checks and postage (Thai PBS, 2017). The government has refunded individual income taxes via the PromptPay up to 90% within three years (Bank of Thailand 2023).

The e-Donation electronic donation system is a platform designed to collect donation information from educational institutions, religious institutions, hospitals, and charitable organizations. Its purpose is to facilitate convenience for donors, allowing them to receive tax benefits without presenting donation receipts to tax authorities. This system enables donors to receive tax refunds more efficiently (Department of Older Persons, 2018). The Revenue Department has issued a directive requiring all donation recipients, including educational institutions, temples, churches, mosques, and other receiving entities, to record donation information in the e-donation system. This directive mandates that tax authorities nationwide educate all donation-receiving organizations to register for a tax identification number starting from January 2018 and refrain from retroactively recording donation data to reduce the corruption issue within the organization (The Revenue Department, 2024).

The government assists low-income individuals through state welfare cards, allocating funds for discounted purchases at designated stores and public transportation expenses, totaling over 96.082 billion baht. Additionally, there is a transfer of funds to welfare cards to aid citizens in various aspects, such as infrastructure development and utility bill assistance, totaling over 52.228 billion THB, benefiting more than 14.6 million welfare card recipients. The government has promoted the integration of social welfare databases, such as "e-Social Welfare," to link information, screen eligible beneficiaries, and directly distribute funds to the public via PromptPay using their national identification numbers instead of cash or checks since late 2016. This distribution includes funds for newborns, elderly allowances, disability allowances, and COVID-19 relief, as well as tax refunds, resulting in a 50.4% increase in funds transferred via PromptPay (multi-item transfers) annually. This initiative will expand to other welfare programs in the future (Bank of Thailand, 2023).

PromptPay also decreases the cost of cash handling in the economic system. Bank of Thailand (BOT) revealed that using cash is three times higher than e-payment, pointing out production and transportation costs amounting to 50 billion THB annually. The costs above are divided into portions, with over 4 billion THB attributed to the BOT and approximately 46 billion THB falling under commercial banks. These costs begin from the stage of banknote printing and transportation to the ten national banknote processing centers. When commercial banks dispense cash, banknotes are transferred to over 100 cash centers nationwide. The banknotes are distributed to ATMs and branches in various regions to accommodate customers' cash withdrawals. The cost of digital transactions remains in the form of fixed costs stemming from infrastructure. Therefore, as digital transactions increase, the average cost will further decrease. BOT stated that digital transactions could reduce the cost of cash handling by 50,000 million THB in 2023. The cost of cheque issuing for social welfare via E-payment was reduced by 87,000 million THB in 2023.

Overall, PromptPay provides digital transaction records, which are helpful for both individuals and organizations for tracking expenses and managing finances. It reduces the

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informal economy as more transactions are recorded electronically. It becomes harder to conduct unreported or informal transactions, thus helping to increase tax compliance and reduce the shadow economy. This system is a powerful tool for enhancing the efficiency, security, and inclusivity of financial transactions in Thailand, contributing significantly to the nation's financial infrastructure and economic development.

Keyword: PromptPay, Digital Payment, Efficiency, Cashless, Electronic Transfer

Introduction

PromptPay is a transformative financial innovation introduced under Thailand's national e-payment scheme, a key component of the broader financial and digital transformation strategy driven by the Thai government. Launched in January 2017 by the Bank of Thailand in collaboration with major banks and financial institutions, PromptPay was designed to revolutionize how individuals and businesses conduct financial transactions by leveraging digital technology to provide a fast, secure, and cost-effective payment system. PromptPay was introduced as part of the Thai government's National e-Payment Master Plan, which aimed to modernize the country's payment infrastructure, promote financial inclusion, and reduce dependency on cash transactions. At its core, PromptPay seeks to enhance financial convenience and accessibility for Thai citizens by providing an electronic payment system that is easily accessible via mobile phones, ATMs, and banking apps.

PromptPay system has been expanded to include various services such as tax refunds, e-social welfare, and e-Donation via PromptPay (Bank of Thailand, 2021). There are number of PromptPay registration 68 million IDs according to the data in 2021 (see Table 1).

Table 1: Number of PromptPay registration

	2020	2021
Number of Mobile/ internet banking accounts	103,643,083	123,232,927 Accounts
Number of PromptPay registration	56,241,457	68,639,304 IDs

Source: Bank of Thailand (2021); Laokulrach, M., & Mangmeechai, A. (2024).

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Figure 1: Timeline of Government policy on Digital transformation in financial services
Source: Bank of Thailand (2021)

The PromptPay and QR code are the mainly e-Payment system that drives Thailand to be a cashless society Somkid Yakean (2020). According to the study of Anassayapa Boonrod and Prasopchai Pasunon (2017), they reported the majority of participants (n=400) obtained information about income tax from the Revenue Department website and possessed prior experience in refunding their personal income tax. Perceived ease of use, perceived risk, and users' trust were significant factors influencing users' choice of PromptPay for personal income tax refunds.

Reduce Donation fraud via E-donation

Corruption remains a persistent global issue, with Thailand itself under close international scrutiny. Despite ongoing efforts, this problem continues to occur in various sectors, including within temples. The results of the Corruption Perception Index (CPI) by Transparency International, an organization dedicated to global transparency, indicate that in the year 2023, Thailand scored 35 out of 100 points. This places Thailand at rank 108 out of 180 countries assessed, dropping seven positions (BangkokPost., 2024).

The e-Donation electronic donation system is a platform designed to collect donation information from educational institutions, religious institutions, hospitals, and charitable organizations. Its purpose is to facilitate convenience for donors, allowing them to enjoy tax benefits without the need to present donation receipts to tax authorities. This system enables donors to receive tax refunds more efficiently (Department of Older Persons, 2018).

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Figure 2: E-donation flow
Source: The revenue department (2024)

The Revenue Department has issued a directive requiring all donation recipients, including educational institutions, temples, churches, mosques, and other receiving entities, to record donation information in the e-Donation system. This directive mandates that tax authorities nationwide educate all donation-receiving organizations to register for a tax identification number starting from January 2018 and refrain from retroactively recording donation data (The revenue department, 2024).

The 'Temple Funds' scandal, involving corruption in the allocation of funds to temples has rocked the Buddhist community. The National Office of Buddhism (NOB) subsequently initiated investigations into the temple funds corruption in collaboration with the Anti-Money Laundering Office (AMLO). Documents revealing financial misconduct and misappropriation of temple funds from 2012 to 2016 were uncovered. These irregularities involved disbursements to support 33 temples. Through these investigations, losses totaling more than 270 million THB were identified (Srisuwanket, T., 2021).

Thailand boasts over 41,000 temples scattered across every region of the country. Temples are heavily involved in financial activities, receiving an average of over 3 billion THB in state subsidies annually, along with donations from merit-making activities such as donation boxes, ordination ceremonies, make and off-season offering of robes and other needs to monks, and more. However, financial management within temples falls under the authority of the abbot, relying on their knowledge and experience in financial accounting. Yet, it remains a concern that unscrupulous individuals may exploit this system for wrongful activities.

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Thai National Statistical Office's Household Socio-Economic Survey for the years 2014 and 2018 found that 56.7 million and 57.8 million people made charitable donations or accounted for 87% of Thai population (National Statistic Office, 2018). This included donations for food, offerings to temples, and contributions to various organizations. The total value of charitable donations in Thailand in 2017 amounted to approximately 130 billion THB, or 6,200 THB per household per year. This represented an increase from around 94 billion THB in 2009, or 5,000 THB per household per year, with an average annual growth rate of 3.8%, which is lower than the nominal GDP growth rate of 6.0% during the same period (ThaiPublica, 2019).

The main focus of Thai donations still lies in the act of 'nurturing spiritual happiness,' which provides an opportunity for continuous giving without end. As for the aspect of 'tax deduction,' it is considered merely a byproduct or one of the 'perks' that comes from donating. Many individuals often donate far beyond their tax exemption limit. Additionally, in the past year, donations through foundations have been eligible for a doubled tax deduction, whereas previously, it was only a single deduction. However, the donation amounts have not significantly increased compared to previous years, remaining at a similar level. Therefore, it is believed that this issue is not the key factor influencing people's decisions to donate through foundations.

Convenience aligned with the changing behavior of donors is crucial. With the increasing number of donors using smartphones, which has become the primary channel for donations, now comprising over 70% (SD Thailand, 2023).

Tax refund

The government has refund individual income taxes via the PromptPay up to 90% within 3 years (Bank of Thailand 2023) (see Table 2).

Table 2: Number of people who submit the tax form and individuals who have tax obligations to fulfill (Million)

Year	Number of people who submit the tax form (Million)			Total	Individuals who have tax obligations to fulfill (Million)	Sources
	Female	Male	Others		Total	
2022				11.52		
2021				10.30	4.17	Posttoday (2023)
2020				10.60	3.95	
2019				11.80	4.02	
2018						
2017	2.84	2.88	5.02	10.74		
2016	3.15	3.13	4.66	10.93		The revenue department (2018)
2015	5.74	3.80	1.16	10.70		
2014	3.55	3.63	3.19	10.38		

Source: Bank of Thailand (2023); Laokulrach, M., & Mangmeechai, A. (2024).

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Mr. Prasong further stated that PromptPay is an alternative system designed to enhance convenience in making and receiving money transfers from government agencies. Additionally, it helps save operational costs by at least 40 THB per transaction, as it eliminates the need for issuing checks and postage (Thai PBS, 2017).

The Revenue Department has closed the Vat tax refund system via check, replacing it with PromptPay transfers instead, starting in 2024 onwards, to prevent fraudulent processes.

Value Added Tax or VAT is a tax on sales of goods or providing services in each production step and sell products or services both manufactured within the country and imported from abroad. Specify cases where taxpayers do not apply for PromptPay. You must pay the tax refund transfer service yourself through your account number. Transferring refunds through the taxpayer's account number will incur a transfer fee of up to 250 THB per transaction. This cost The Department cannot be the bearer of such a burden. This is because the number of such transactions or refund transfers is large, or approximately 3-4 hundred thousand items. At the same time, the taxpayer is unwilling to bear the burden of such expenses (Thansettakij, 2023).

E-social welfare

The government provides assistance to low-income individuals through state welfare cards, allocating funds for discounted purchases at designated stores, public transportation expenses, totaling over 96.082 billion baht. Additionally, there is a transfer of funds to welfare cards to aid citizens in various aspects such as infrastructure development, utility bill assistance, totaling over 52.228 billion THB, benefiting more than 14.6 million welfare card recipients. The government has promoted the integration of social welfare databases (e-Social Welfare) to link information, screen eligible beneficiaries, and directly distribute funds to the public via PromptPay using their national identification numbers, instead of cash or checks, since late 2016. This includes funds for newborns, elderly allowances, disability allowances, and COVID-19 relief, as well as tax refunds, resulting in a 50.4% increase in funds transferred via PromptPay (multi-item transfers) annually. This initiative will be expanded to other welfare programs in the future (Bank of Thailand, 2023).

Analysis

Cost-benefit analysis (CBA) is a fundamental tool employed in various fields to evaluate the feasibility and desirability of projects, policies, and interventions. The costs and benefits associated with Promptpay have been gathered from a variety of credible sources.

Reducing cost of cash handling

In the year 2022, Thailand had banknotes in circulation totaling 2.1 trillion baht, resulting in a total cost of nearly 50 billion THB. This is the "Cost of Cash Handling," which is not just the expenses related to production or printing of banknotes alone, but also includes: Counting and sorting costs, Transportation and storage costs, Expenses for maintaining security, Insurance costs, Travel expenses, Risks of loss, Withdrawal fees, Costs of commercial bank management, and Destruction costs (Thairat Money, 2023).

Bank of Thailand (BoT) revealed that the cost of using cash is three times higher than e-Payment, pointing out production and transportation costs amounting to 50 billion THB per

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year. The aforementioned costs are divided into portions, with over 4 billion baht attributed to the BoT, and the remaining approximately 46 billion THB falling under commercial banks. These costs begin from the stage of banknote printing and transportation to the 10 national banknote processing centers. When commercial banks dispense cash, there is a subsequent transfer of banknotes to over 100 cash centers nationwide. Following this, the banknotes are distributed to ATMs and branches in various regions to accommodate cash withdrawals by customers.

However, the cost-incurred steps of cash usage don't end here. There is a reverse transportation process back to the BoT to destroy worn-out banknotes and deposit funds with the BoT, aiming to reduce the cash handling costs for the banks themselves (Kamonwan Madaiyang, 2022).

The cost of digital transactions still remains in the form of fixed costs stemming from infrastructure. Therefore, as digital transactions increase, the average cost will further decrease.

Table 3: Summarized cost and benefits of Promptpay

	Money circulates	Number of registers	Cost reduction	Sources
Caseless economy			Cost of handling cashes -50,000 million THB	(Thairat Money, 2023)
E-donation	130 billion THB (in 2017)	57.8 million (in 2018)		(ThaiPublica, 2019)
Tax refund		3.75 million (90%*4.17) (in 2021)		BoT (2023)
E-social welfare	52.228 billion baht	14.6 million welfare card recipients	Cost of Cheque -87,000 Million THB (2.2% reduction YoY)	BoT (2023)

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Conclusions

PromptPay is a cornerstone of Thailand's national e-payment initiative, designed to enable faster, more convenient, and secure financial transactions. Its benefits span multiple areas, including convenience, cost savings, accessibility, and support for the digital economy.

PromptPay facilitates real-time money transfers between banks, significantly improving upon traditional methods that could take hours or days. Transactions can be completed at any time, without being limited by banking hours. This seamless process is accompanied by lower transaction fees compared to traditional methods, with many smaller transactions being free of charge. The registration process is simple, allowing users to link their bank accounts to their national ID number or mobile phone number. This broadens access, making PromptPay available to anyone with a bank account and enhancing financial inclusivity across the country. PromptPay incorporates robust security measures, such as encryption and two-factor authentication, to protect user data and transactions, ensuring a safe platform for financial activities. PromptPay plays a crucial role in facilitating online payments, simplifying the process for businesses and consumers. By encouraging digital transactions, it supports the growth of Thailand's digital economy, making e-commerce more accessible and attractive. The government leverages PromptPay to distribute social welfare benefits, tax refunds, and other payments directly to citizens. This eliminates delays associated with physical checks and streamlines the distribution process. By making electronic transactions accessible and convenient, PromptPay helps reduce reliance on cash, promoting a cashless society. This shift improves economic efficiency and decreases costs linked to cash handling. PromptPay creates digital records of transactions, assisting individuals and businesses in tracking expenses and managing finances. This transparency helps reduce unreported transactions, increases tax compliance, and diminishes the shadow economy.

In summary, PromptPay is a transformative financial tool that enhances the efficiency, security, and inclusivity of financial transactions in Thailand. It significantly contributes to the nation's financial infrastructure and fosters economic development by supporting digitalization and financial modernization.

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